

Original Research Article

Do Teenagers See Room for Dreams in Mathematics Classes?

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ABSTRACT: Based on the authors Paulo Freire, Ole Skovsmose, and Emmanuel Lévinas, as well as philosophers connected to the traditional school, this text intends to pursue a particular research question within the general objective of my ongoing thesis, namely, “How do teenagers see room for dreams in mathematics classes?” It is qualitative research, inspired by the methods of case study and oral history. Data production was carried out with adolescents from two schools: one located in Brazil and the other in Colombia. Semi-structured interviews and discussion groups were carried out, and the data production took place in 2019. I address some theoretical concepts regarding the concept of dreams, as well as aspects related to what we recognize as a traditional school. After that, I present an initial analysis, based on students’ discussions about possible room at school for teenagers’ dreams. In the sequence, I highlight students’ opinions about room for dreams in mathematics classes. As a result, I conclude that a closed mathematics based on the “exercise paradigm” does not establish relationships with students and does not open space for their dreams.

KEYWORDS: *dreams; foregrounds; dialogue; alterity; teenagers; exercise paradigm; mathematics education*

Biotto Filho (2015), when carrying out his doctoral research in a community that involved socially disadvantaged youth, identified that most of the boys interviewed by him had the dream of being a soccer player. He thought the reason they expressed this desire was because they enjoyed playing soccer; but investigating further, he realized that, in fact, boys saw in this sport the possibility of social ascension. Thus, Biotto Filho concluded that it is impossible to disassociate dreams and social perspectives.

This was also revealed in my experience as a teacher. From a very young age, working in public schools, I was concerned with the students’ dreams and with the purpose of helping make their dreams come true. I highlight an episode from my trajectory: When I was working at a high school, in early 2017, I had the opportunity to interview all students from two classes about their dreams. They presented dreams for themselves, and for their families. Some highlighted the intention of following professions linked to their favorite disciplines, others wanted to follow the guidelines of

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their parents, and others hid their most intimate dreams from colleagues and families. What drove them to make these choices? How does their social context and school influence these choices? And what is the role of mathematics classes in this? For this purpose, I will focus on making some theoretical considerations in the following paragraphs.

For Freire (1992), *dreaming* is not a mere desire: it is a political act, the result of the social-historical connotation of being women and men in this world. It's a way of making and remaking history, as people who not only fit in and adapt to the world, but also intend to transform it. The boys interviewed by Biotto Filho (2015), for example, want to transform their social reality and, therefore, want to transform their world. Perhaps this was also the case for the students I interviewed in 2017.

The origin of every dream and every man's quest, for Freire (1983), is the awareness of his 'unfinishedness'. In other words, it is the desire to be more. Men and women know that they are unfinished and that is why they dream, educate themselves. Another concept related to dreaming is that of the 'foreground'. I will write about this in the next section.

A *foreground* (Skovsmose, 2012, 2014) is a concept that refers to a person's prospects, full of possibilities and obstructions, hopes and fears. This scope of a person's aspirations is related to their background (D'Ambrosio, 1990), that is, their life experiences, their cultural environment, their fulfilled and frustrated dreams. Thus, despite the foregrounds of a person (or a group) being related to past experiences, which generate impacts and drive you in some way to the future, the foregrounds are opaque—an uncertain concept, susceptible to change. Hypothetically, I understand that the aspirations present in students' foregrounds interfere in their dreams, in their relationship with the school, and in the subject of mathematics, as they interfere in their life prospects.

I also note that the philosopher Lévinas' thought—as well as Freire's—is understood as being based on the idea of the unfinished state of human being. For him (Lévinas, 2007), there is something beyond what influences us, which is not under our control, and which is never exhausted: this something is in the *exteriority*. And what is this exteriority? It is a movement of transcendence of the human being, a metaphysical movement that turns outwards, that turns to the other human being.

Finally, another movement through which the human being can put himself, during the exercise of being more, is that of *alterity*. This concept, from the perspective of Lévinas (2007), can be understood as the ability to put yourself in the other's shoes and to take responsibility for them. Despite being recognized that the other is not himself, it is through alterity that he sees the other not as a stranger or enemy, but as a being as unfinished as he is, full of multiple possibilities.

Faced with the concepts presented by Freire, Skovsmose, and Lévinas, I turn to the young students' dreams in a socially disadvantaged situation. How are these students' foregrounds constituted? To what extent have they transcended their own history, their background? How has the school operated to problematize the social context of these young people, though promoting transcendence? And especially, are mathematics classes collaborating in this process?

Regarding these concerns, which began during my master's degree (Soares, 2008), I dedicated myself during my Ph.D. to carry out a literary review of theses and dissertations that could help me answer these questions. Nonetheless, no works were found that were dedicated to the study of students' dreams in mathematics education, and equally few, that did so in a way related to the concepts of foreground and dreams. In this sense, I understand that this research theme is unprecedented.

Research Question and Aim

After this brief introduction and theoretical discussion, I present the aim of this text, which represents a particularity of the aims of my PhD thesis. Therefore, I concentrate my efforts here on answering, “How do teenagers see room for dreams in mathematics classes?” Thus, I highlight the methodological procedures that enabled me to study what students think about the space for dreams in mathematics classes, and then, I present some findings.

Methods and Procedures

This is a qualitative research based on Goldenberg (2004), developed in two first-year-High-School classrooms,² with students aged between 15 and 16 years one at a Federal Institute of São Paulo (IFSP), in a rural municipality in the state of São Paulo, Brazil; and another at a District Educative Institution (IED) on the outskirts of Bogotá, Colombia. Both schools serve mostly socially disadvantaged students.

It is important to clarify that, since the beginning of this work, the intention was not to carry out a comparative study between the two nations, but to gather elements from the experiences of data production in the two schools, in order to expand possibilities.

Although this research is not based on a specific methodology and can be considered, therefore, its own method, it is still possible to highlight some inspirations. On the one hand, it is inspired by the qualitative research method called case study (Goldenberg, 2004), and on the other hand, the life history method (Nogueira, 2017).

With the mathematics teacher’s help, I presented the research in the classrooms, seeking volunteer students to participate. Data production involved discussion groups with these students. At the IFSP, this process took place in August 2019 at the IED, in September of the same year. The concepts of unfinishedness, history as a possibility, foregrounds, and dreams were part of these procedures, even though many of these terms were not directly used in the construction of the discussion group script.

The discussion groups were held at each school, lasting approximately one-and-a-half-hours each. All discussions were audio and video recorded, in order to facilitate transcriptions that were made later. The theme that is addressed in this text is presented below:

THEME: The dreams possibilities at school.
Do you see spaces/room at school for the discussion/fostering of teenagers’ dreams? Talk about it. And in math classes?

Figure 1. Theme addressed during the discussion groups.

For data analysis, the transcriptions were based on Skovsmose (2014). Finally, with the transcripts in hand, we observed how the concepts of dreams, foregrounds, and transcendence emerged from the data.

All the concepts presented here will be important in the section where I present the research data. I am now dedicating myself to making a brief presentation about the traditional mathematics

² In the Brazilian school system, it was in a 1st-year-Secondary-School classroom, and in the Colombian school system, it was in a 10th-year-Secondary-School classroom.

class, and then carrying out connections with the practice evidenced by the students participating in the research.

The School Tradition

In the traditional school of the philosophy of education, the school was the place that holds knowledge, and students would develop their reason through the knowledge that they learned in that place. The social context, with its marks, setbacks, and great possibilities, would not be part of the school.

Undoubtedly, mathematics classes are influenced by this tradition and this fact persists to the present day. A key thinker for understanding the traditional mathematics class is René Descartes. He took the understanding that knowledge must develop reason very seriously. This French philosopher and mathematician wrote, in the 17th century, that knowledge is innate to being, and therefore all knowledge comes from interiority, and not from external factors (Descartes, 1955). Therefore, he believed that knowledge originated from good thinking, and in his searching for the ‘true knowledge’, he found mathematics. This area of knowledge, with its demonstrations and rigidity seemed to him to be the most favorable environment for safe and true reason. He began to take a path that started from doubts to reach certainties, departing from “I doubt, therefore I think” and arriving at the famous “I think, therefore I am” (Aranha, 1996).

Contemporaneously, Skovsmose (2001) carried out a study of the traditional mathematics class. He understands that the way students usually learn mathematics is based on a type of paradigm: the *exercise paradigm*. According to Skovsmose, this paradigm refers to the endless lists of technical exercises that are often disconnected from reality, usually formulated by an authority outside the classroom (most often taken from the textbook), and whose objective is undoubtedly finding the right answer. In this model, the learning of mathematics occurs through the exhaustion of technical repetition. I add that this teaching paradigm is linked to the concept of knowledge transmission (Soares & Civiero, 2017), which discourages listening to students as part of the learning process, and prioritizes individual work over collective work.

From the above, some questions become important: How do students see mathematics classes? Do they come close to what is meant by a traditional mathematics class? Does this type of class contribute to the students’ dreams? I understand that these questions are connected to the main question of this text. In the next section, I reflect on these issues, while at the same time trying to bring closer, or distant, the concepts that were problematized in the previous section from the answers that students presented about spaces or room for dreams in mathematics classes.

What Room for Dreams Already Exists in Mathematics Classes?

Eight students participated in the discussion group held at the Colombian school, who were divided into two groups that interacted with each other. In Brazil, seven students participated, also divided into two groups. All of them trying the answering the questions: Do you see spaces/room at school for the discussion/fostering of teenagers’ dreams? Talk about it. And in mathematics classes?

In general, all the students who took part in this research consider that academic subjects at school, and mathematics in particular, present little or no space for dreams. Let’s see, for example, Giselle’s speech, who showed that she didn’t find any room for dreams in the school environment, although she considered the IFSP a more favorable place for the topic:

Giselle: About the first part, if the school has this space, I think that schools, in general, end up not thinking much about this issue of the dreams. I think the IFSP is a more open place for that, but still very closed on this. I don't think anyone (at school) really thinks about it [...]

In her speech, she demonstrates that she understands that making room for dreams implies greater opening up of the school and, at this point, we establish the connections between the concepts of unfinishedness and dreams. A school that understands itself as *unfinished* is an open school which values freedom, and which recognizes the importance of considering the experiences and needs of students for the movement to be greater. Later, the student added, highlighting how she sees the room for dreams in mathematics classes:

Giselle: I think mathematics is the subject that gives less space for this.

Flávio, who was in the other group, didn't identify much room for dreams either. Notice, in the first excerpt that follows, that dreams and prospects for the future are terminologies used as synonyms for him, and that they were connected to the professional context. In this sense, dreams are understood as part of the foreground, responsible for generating perspectives for the future. In the second excerpt, the same student shows how difficult it would be for him to find such spaces in mathematics classes:

Flávio: [...] if a person is interested in mathematics, it is through mathematics classes that he will know if he will continue with this objective. So, for me, this is the only way that math class influences our future, in our professional choice [...]

Flávio: [...] How would it be possible to create more spaces for future perspectives in math classes? I don't know, because [it seems to me that] there's no way.

At IED, a dialogue on this subject in the group in which students Andrea, Jhon, Tania and Martha took part started from a reflection on the school in general, and then focused on mathematics classes:

Andrea: That happens when teachers talk to us about it... but I think there are very few [teachers that do].

Jhon: Fernando is the only one.

Tania: Fernando.

Jhon: He's the only one that says, "come here, think about what you do."

Tania: We hardly talk about our future with them, so we don't know...

Jhon: They are hardly interested in knowing.

Andrea: And in math classes?

Martha: Ah... this [teacher] doesn't talk about the future.

It is important to note in this dialogue, that—according to Jhon—in addition to saying that teachers almost never give room for dreams in their classes, this happens because they “are not interested in knowing.” This student reinforced this argument further when he revealed to me the fact that he didn't see much space for dreams at school:

Jhon: In this school there is hardly any such room, and there are very few teachers who are interested in seeing us doing well. Here [at this school] there must be about two or three who ask us “how's life going?”, or “think about the future”, “change some

things”, “be a better person”, and so on. Well, but we have some spaces, but not in the school itself, but among friends.

In this speech, it is evident that—according to Jhon—spaces for dreams are moments of dialogue and that, in the classroom, would occur when the teacher shows interest in the student’s life, and in their future prospects. This would happen, therefore, when the teacher puts himself in the student’s place, in a relationship of alterity (Lévinas, 2007). The student believes that most of the time, this room for dreams happens between friends. Most of the students at the school in Bogotá agreed with Jhon’s opinion, including people from the other group, noting that they especially didn’t see spaces for dreams in their mathematics classes. However, Claudia and Jhonatan, from the other group, exposed new opinions about room for dreams. Let’s see the dialogue:

Claudia: Yes, everywhere like you said. With friends... sometimes talking to teachers. Now about the second question, which is about mathematics, I don’t think so. Our teacher never...

Jennifer: In math, no.

Jhonatan: The thing is, I already had some conversations with the math teacher. When I got really depressed, the teacher noticed [...]

Later, when I addressed the group, Jeimy—who was part of the same group as Claudia, Jennifer, and Jhonatan—added:

Jeimy: What we thought [...]—well, actually, it’s more personal—is that there are a lot of moments during classes, but they can also occur at breaks or other times. But during the class the theme of the dream may appear. Teachers often ask a question, giving as an example someone in the class: “And you, what do you want to do in the future?” And it is in those moments that we think about our dreams... or as the other group said, this also happens with friends, during a conversation, when one will say “I want to do this [...]”

In other words, Claudia believes that moments of dialogue between teachers and students can happen, but not during mathematics classes. Jeimy already believes that these spaces are more common than other colleagues think, and Jhonatan even expressed a personal moment in which he and the mathematics teacher had already engaged in a personal dialogue.

In summary, in both schools most students reported finding little room for dreams at school, and even less so during mathematics classes. Even so, when this space existed, they took place through teacher-student dialogues, at times in which teachers had concerns about the lives and future of students. In other words, the students expressed that a possible room for dreams to be discussed and fostered during mathematics classes would take place through the strengthening of personal relationships between teacher and students. In other words, this would happen through alterity relationships.

It is important to highlight one last argument: Some students identified that mathematics does help them to make their dreams come true from a technical point of view. For example, Martha, an IED student, pointed out that, despite not seeing room for dreams in mathematics classes, she sees that the classes help young people to make their dreams come true in another way:

Martha: Ah... this [teacher] doesn’t talk about the future. But like that, the person should learn, because mathematics for a person is like oxygen, because if a person doesn’t know how to add up, he’s lost. Because, for everything, you need numbers [...]

In other words, the student highlighted that the technical knowledge provided by mathematics classes is essential for life: after all, “for a person it is like oxygen.” Brenda, a student at the São Paulo school, when talking about dreams, also reinforced the importance of mathematical knowledge for life:

Brenda: I think mathematics influences a lot, because generally we are, for example, counting how many blouses we are going to wear in a day, how many calculations we are going to do today, etc. So, math is not just a class, we kind of use math all the time.

In other words, although many students do not see spaces to talk about the future during mathematics classes or to reflect explicitly on their dreams, some of them believe that it contributes to that future indirectly, through knowledge that is provided in the classroom. Thus, based on the theoretical discussion that I explained in the previous section, I conclude that: regardless of the traditional character of mathematics classes, its transmissive teaching feature, and the technical knowledge that is experienced during classes, in the opinion of these students, mathematics classes contribute to young people’s lives so that they may fulfill their dreams.

Some Final Reflections

Mathematics classes seem to be even more focused on developing technical knowledge than on dialogue with society and relationships with people. The heritage that these classes carry, coming from traditional philosophies of education, make their abstract and precise aspect overlap, covering their historical and human aspect. The exercise paradigm (Skovsmose, 2001) still seems to be the prevailing one, and naturally it does not make room for the development of more humanized relationships between teachers and their students.

Although technical knowledge has its important value, even as a promoter of dreams (since mathematical knowledge is practiced beyond the classroom and can be part of the professional dreams of many students), it is not enough. The approach based strictly on exercises, which aim only at the right answer, and which are barely related to the contexts or aspirations of the students, do not establish a connection with their backgrounds, much less open room for the development of their foregrounds. A closed mathematics, which does not allow for questions or uncertainty, does not establish relationships with the unfinishedness that is part of every human being and therefore does not open up to the new, does not connect to the human desire to be more. In other words, to connect with students, mathematics should be as open as they are. And finally, something happened when the relationships between teachers and students are as closed as the work in the exercise paradigm. Instead of dialogue, what is seen is a relationship of authority from the teacher towards the student, the role of the school as a transmitter of knowledge is reinforced, and the possibility of alterity relations is ended.

To have more room in mathematics classes for fostering dreams, it is therefore necessary to break with the exercise paradigm, create more dialogical relationships between teacher and students, and expand the boundaries between mathematical knowledge, history, and society. Thus, in addition to contributing to students’ dreams from a technical point of view, mathematics classes can also contribute to their dreams from a human point of view.

References

Aranha, M. L. de A. (1996). *Filosofia da educação*. Moderna.

- Biotto Filho, D. (2015). *Quem não sonhou em ser um jogador de futebol? Trabalho com projetos para reelaborar foregrounds* [Doctoral dissertation, Universidade Estadual Paulista (UNESP)–Rio Claro]. Repositório Institucional UNESP. <http://hdl.handle.net/11449/124075>
- D'Ambrosio, U. (1990). *Etnomatemática: Arte ou técnica de explicar e conhecer*. Ática.
- Freire, P. (1983). *Educação e mudança*. Eds. Paz e Terra.
- Freire, P. (1992). *Pedagogia da esperança*. Eds. Paz e Terra.
- Goldenberg, M. (2004). *A arte de pesquisar: como fazer pesquisa qualitativa em Ciências Sociais*. Record.
- Lévinas, E. (2007). *Totality and infinity: An essay on exteriority*. Duquesne University Press.
- Nogueira, M. L. M., de Barros, V. A., Araujo, A. D. G., & Pimenta, D. A. O. (2017). O método de história de vida: a exigência de um encontro em tempos de aceleração. *Pesquisas e Práticas Psicossociais*, 12(2), 466–485.
- Skovsmose, O. (2001). Landscapes of investigation. *ZDM*, 33(4), 123–132.
- Skovsmose, O. (2012). Students' foregrounds: Hope, despair, uncertainty. *Pythagoras*, 33(2), Article 162. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4102/pythagoras.v33i2.162>
- Skovsmose, O. (2014). *Foregrounds: Opaque stories about learning*. Sense Publishers.
- Soares, D. A. (2008). *Educação matemática crítica: Contribuições para o debate teórico e seus reflexos nos trabalhos acadêmicos*. [Unpublished Master's Thesis]. Pontifícia Universidade Católica de São Paulo (PUC-SP): São Paulo, Brazil.
- Soares, D. A.; & Cíviero, P. A. G. (2017). Problematizando a racionalidade técnica por meio dos ambientes de aprendizagem da educação matemática crítica. *VIII Congreso Iberoamericano de educación matemática*. Madrid, Spain.